

The future initial class teachers poetic works on to work to teach in education application reach

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Abstract: This in the article start drinking class teachers poetic works on to work to teach in education how application to be done about information is given This is the article method how make up and how to the results reach deadlines , as well students for this method how useful will be and to them how help wants to give to be possible describes . Abstract of the author the goal and problems determination , implementation and the results explanation for practical information will give . This is research in the article annotation , beginning class to their teachers poetic works on to work in education how support possible about scientific instructions before pushing goes

Key words: information , skill , qualification , self on work , method , methodology , shery works

Access: Get started class teachers poetic works on to work learning for the following methods in education application reach can :

1. Poetic works dating and analysis to do : To the students classic poetry and modern of the poem main features about information give to them you know that's it in terms of help give takes
2. Poetry concepts teaching : Students with poems on negotiations , submissions and textbook exercises through of poetry concepts strengthening
3. Poem texts to emphasize and translation to do : To the students something poem the text emphasizing your training , then him translation to do help give you will get
4. The poem creative sides with Introduction : Readers with together poem to create done increasing them creative sides with by introducing exit
5. Poetry history and culture about information to give : to students of poetry history , culture and importance about information giving them this in the field progress to do your encouragement can

These methods done increase and start drinking class to their teachers poetic works love with to learn and his importance understand for help give you will get

Main part : Get started class teachers poetic works on to work to teach in education very important This is the style of the students spiritual and aesthetic experiences development , creative their thinking deepening and their his own poetry abilities to strengthen help will give . Poetic works on work education to students verb practices through skills to develop possibility will give . This style through , readers work on analysis do , of the text meaning and the recitation explanation of the poet thought and feeling with getting to know exit and him to vacation help will give . Get started in classes poetic works on of work one series advantages there is . Such training of students language knowledge strengthens and them word written art with introduces . Also poetic works on work through students creative thinking developing them independent victory winning to be help will give . Get started class of teachers poetic works on to work in education application to reach very important This is style through students spiritual to modernity have being creative and opinionated to people rotating creator to power have will be Education in institutions this style by developing to go Demand because this all on the side user for much useful and efficient will be

First class teachers for poetic works on to work education to give very important They are that's it age students for progress method information give , historical events or of people in his life important from events from the debate information get , details and concepts to explain help to give need Also poetic works on work in classes creativity develops and to students own ideas expression to do chance will give . This is the method through students history and to literature interests calling take out their creative and mental abilities to develop help will give .

Discussion : Start class teachers poetic works on to work to teach for the following steps useful will be :

1. Teachers for examples and samples present achievement : Poetic works on to work learning for , teachers for examples and samples show useful will be This is theirs more understandable to understand and strengthening help will give .

2. Analysis to do to teach : In poetry how features identify exit and to them theory cause exit to students main help will be The teacher , the poem analysis to do and in it goals to determine to students to teach need

3. Discussion and debate practices : Students with poem on regularly discussion and discussions through their his opinion expression to do possibility to be given it is necessary This is theirs analytical their thinking develops and to questions right answer give will receive in forms their thinking strengthening help will give .

4. Creativity development : Poem on work through , students their creativity develop and their own proud creative approaches appear they will Teacher , their news with that he is not engaged stimulating and creative thoughts development need

5. Personal goals designation : Har one of the student poetic in works goals different to be that it is possible attention focus need A teacher , every one of the student personal goals suitable respectively help give received without to them advice to give it is necessary

6. Manuals with work : Poem on working lesson during important from manuals use to the goal according to will be These are the guides through students poetry about independent studies done increase they get

A poem on of work practice personal to goals suitable clarity depends and this on the way standard from programs external one of the assignments little task presence importance is a big issue .

this purpose reach for the following roads take you go can :

1. Poetic works on of work skills teaching : Teacher to students poem analysis , images , color loss and another poetic works on of work technique teach

2. To the students independent the work or project give : Har one student his own selected poetic work on independent the work or the project done to increase need It's up to them of students thoughts increasing their creative properties and abilities develops .

3. Discussion and negotiations organize Occupation : Teacher and students between poetic works on discussion and negotiation organize reach very important This is the method through students thought said , questions giving an explanation give and support .

4. Creator activities : Poetry works in education in your training your application very important An example for from poems consists of collages to create a poem dramatic in the theater to create or even new poem to create can

5. Students efforts designation : Har one student for goals specify and of them come when you come out , their efforts with to engage in possibility give important these recommendations using , next initial class teachers poetic works on to work appeal do it !

Summary

Get started class teachers poetic works on to work to teach in education the most good from the roads one to be can This method is for students meaningful texts Create and in them care to understand help will give . For example , poetic works on additional songs write stories dramatization to do or own his works to create show

through students looking for topic about more to understand they achieve That's the way , students for famous a poet and writers introducing them creative activities research which and they are with together thought exchange for the ground creates Such famous a poet and writers between Mirza Great bek , Alisher Like Navoi , Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur individuals show me

Used books

1. " Poetry and methodology " - G. Makhkamov
2. Uzbek people poetry " - M. Fozilov
3. Uzbek literature history " - A. Kadyrov
4. " Poetry and poem theory " - A. Abdullaev
5. " Works on lectures " - A. Khalpulatov

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